

Supplementary Information

New long-acting [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-DFO GLP-1 PET tracers with increased molar activity and reduced kidney accumulation

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Table S1. GLP-1R potency of peptides with and without Zirconium shown as EC₅₀-values (geometric means) in M. 95% confidence intervals indicated for peptide **1** and peptides tested in vivo (**13**, **18** and **19**) are shown in square brackets

DFO load: HSA conc (w/v): Peptide	-Zr		+Zr	
	0%	1%	0%	1%
1	1.90E-12 [1.1E-12, 3.1E-12]	8.40E-11 [7.1E-11, 1E-10]		
3	1.20E-11	1.70E-10	6.80E-12	1.10E-10
4	1.10E-11	1.60E-10	6.80E-12	1.00E-10
5	7.40E-12	1.60E-10	5.70E-12	1.50E-10
6	2.70E-11	3.40E-10	7.90E-12	1.60E-10
7	1.60E-11	3.10E-10	6.90E-12	1.70E-10
8	7.50E-11	1.20E-09	1.10E-10	1.80E-09
9	1.20E-10	3.00E-09	1.30E-10	2.70E-09
10	2.00E-11	8.10E-10	5.50E-11	5.40E-10
11	8.50E-11	1.70E-09	1.10E-11	2.20E-10
12	1.90E-11	3.70E-10	7.60E-12	6.70E-11
13	5.60E-12	1.40E-10	2.90E-12 [1.8E-12, 4.7E-12]	1.00E-10 [7.8E-11, 1.4E-10]
14	1.30E-11	4.10E-10	2.10E-11	1.90E-10
15	3.60E-11	6.00E-10	2.00E-11	3.00E-10
16	1.40E-11	3.10E-10	5.60E-12	2.80E-10
17	1.00E-11	3.10E-10	1.20E-11 7.20E-12	1.90E-10 2.60E-10
18	2.30E-11	5.60E-10	[6.0E-12, 8.7E-12] 2.60E-12	[2.1E-10, 3.2E-10] 1.00E-10
19	2.80E-12	1.60E-10	[1.4E-12, 4.9E-12]	[7.1E-11, 1.5E-10]

Table S2. Radiolabelling efficiency and molar activity (A_m) at different amounts of zirconium per peptide

Peptide	20 MBq/nmol		30 MBq/nmol						60 MBq/nmol		120 MBq/nmol	
	Lab eff (%)	A_m (MBq/nmol)	Lab eff (%)			A_m (MBq/nmol)			Lab eff (%)	A_m (MBq/nmol)	Lab eff (%)	A_m (MBq/nmol)
			Exp 1	Exp 2	Exp 3	Exp 1	Exp 2	Exp 3				
2	44.8	8.81	17.1	42.6	ND	4.8	12.8	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
4	55.9	11.51	51.2	ND	ND	15.4	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
5	37	7.34	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
13	84	17.15	56.6	71.9	72.3	15.9	21.6	21.7	91.5	54.9	ND	ND
16	94.5	18.66	58.4	73.8	77.7	16.3	22.5	23.3	ND	ND	ND	ND
17	89.4	18.68	56.5	80.9	80.0	15.9	24.6	24.0	ND	ND	ND	ND
18	86	17.71	86.9	ND	ND	26.0	ND	ND	ND	ND	69.0	83.6
19	49.5	10.23	19.6	ND	ND	5.5	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND

Table S3. Stability of peptides radiolabelled with 20 MBq/nmol over time in phosphate buffered saline (PBS), fetal calf serum (FCS) and 1000 equiv of EDTA in mQ (EDTA)

Incubation media: Time point: Peptide	Zirconium chelated to peptide (%)																	
	PBS						FCS						EDTA					
	1h	2h	4h	24h	72h	168h	1h	2h	4h	24h	72h	168h	1h	2h	4h	24h	72h	168h
2	41.6	39.6	34.4	28.3	28.6	25	50.6	50.7	46.6	42.3	42.6	31.2	19.6	19	7.7	4.7	1.7	1.3
4	62.3	54.3	32.3	33.5	14.9	6.8	69.9	73	71.5	71.2	69.1	48.2	41.7	81.3	8	6.3	0.9	0.9
5	37	38.4	17.4	13	9.1	5.7	40.4	42.8	31.6	31.7	27	16.9	14.8	45.4	1.9	1.7	0.5	0.5
13	83	85.5	91.3	79.5	68.9	43.8	95	96.6	96.7	89.2	91.7	84.9	88.6	92.4	92	72.8	64.8	31.7
16	94.7	96	94.9	85.1	83	65.4	97.3	97.6	94	86.8	74.7	72.5	96.3	94.1	98.9	89	87.5	63.2
17	95.3	98.4	98.1	88.4	75	48.4	98.4	95.6	98.5	95.5	89.5	78.7	94.7	96	97.3	83.6	83.1	42
18	89.9	93.4	90.9	83.8	76	48.8	96.1	97.7	97.7	95.3	96.7	90.2	89.4	90.1	91.8	78.6	81.2	43.7
19	42.2	27.6	28.3	18.2	10.9	9.3	53.4	56.2	51.7	48.1	47.3	31.9	26.4	16.4	6.8	2.6	1	1.6

Table S4. Stability of peptides radiolabelled with 30 MBq/nmol over time with 1000 equiv of EDTA in mQ

		Zirconium chelated to peptide (%)													
Time point:		1h		2h		4h	24h		96h		120h		144h	168h	
Peptide		Exp 1	Exp 2	Exp 1	Exp 2	Exp 2	Exp 1	Exp 1	Exp 2						
2			76.4		76.6	62.6		36.4		15.6		15.4			11.9
4			79.0		77.4	70.8		59.2		34.5		39.7			30.5
13		98.0	94.7	97.0	93.4	90.1	88.6	79.7	73.7	64.1	68.0	66.5	74.7	67.2	54.5
16		99.0	98.3	96.0	92.0	90.7	89.1	86.6	79.3	71.3	78.4	72.1	75.1	69.8	66.5
17		99.0	94.1	99.0	95.1	94.1	90.2	92.9	85.5	82.2	79.3	87.0	76.4	92.7	81.2
18			94.8		95.6	98.7		92.8		81.6		81.2			77.9

Table S5. Stability of peptides radiolabelled with 60 or 120 MBq/nmol over time with 1000 equiv of EDTA in mQ

		Zirconium chelated to peptide (%)													
Radiolabel:		60 MBq/nmol							120 MBq/nmol						
Time point:		1h	2h	4h	24h	96	120	168	1h	2h	4h	24h	96	120	168
Peptide															
13		97.1	94.8	92.6	87.7	85.2	85.4	78.2	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
18		ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	83.8	82.5	84.3	79.3	76.2	79.4	75.4

Table S6. Biodistribution of [³H]2 by quantitative whole-body autoradiography (QWBA) after intravenous administration for selected tissues at 24 and 72h (data from¹)

Tissue:	% ID / g								
	Blood	Muscle	Lung	Spleen	Liver	Bone marrow	Kidney	Brain	Pancreas
24 h	1.16	0.15	1.07	0.17	0.46	0.19	2.21	0.02	0.22
72 h	0.22	0.02	0.08	0.02	0.05	0.03	0.33	0	0.04

Table S7. Biodistribution of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-2 by gamma counting after intravenous administration for selected tissues at 24 and 72h (data from¹)

Time point	Tissue:	% ID / g								
		Blood	Muscle	Lung	Spleen	Liver	Bone marrow	Kidney	Brain	Pancreas
	Animal #									
24 h	1	0.287	0.088	1.629	0.548	1.133	1.079	8.664	0.015	0.160
	2	0.242	0.078	1.586	0.418	0.822	1.168	7.403	0.013	0.205
	3	0.232	0.064	1.360	0.537	1.347	ND	8.240	0.021	0.207
	4	0.180	0.055	1.337	0.435	1.083	0.855	8.901	0.021	0.206
	5	0.219	0.050	1.523	0.501	1.119	0.865	8.136	0.020	0.239
72 h	1	0.028	0.052	0.738	0.358	0.704	0.341	7.178	0.006	0.145
	2	0.023	0.055	0.947	0.392	0.958	0.436	7.516	0.006	0.164
	3	0.049	0.037	1.339	0.513	0.892	0.461	9.045	0.014	0.491
	4	0.048	0.039	1.199	0.485	0.893	0.492	9.141	0.013	0.381
	5	0.036	0.042	1.246	0.555	1.109	0.700	9.944	0.016	0.421

Table S8. Biodistribution of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-13 by gamma counting after intravenous administration for selected tissues at 24 h

Animal #	% ID / g					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Blood	0.363	0.325	0.343	0.269	0.298	0.267
Heart	0.231	0.222	0.216	0.190	0.204	0.177
Lung	0.659	0.655	0.707	0.753	0.664	0.593
Spleen	0.574	0.619	0.656	0.560	0.584	0.583
Liver	1.819	1.949	1.865	1.764	1.662	1.516
Pancreas	0.287	0.210	0.256	0.211	0.231	0.186
Kidney	7.565	7.668	7.872	6.684	6.577	6.546
Stomach	0.195	0.183	0.179	0.169	0.158	0.158
Stomach-duodenum	0.401	0.276	0.288	0.245	0.248	0.238
Duodenum	0.263	0.188	0.218	0.196	0.193	0.192
Intestine	0.225	0.163	0.223	0.211	0.182	0.185
Colon	0.250	0.208	0.224	0.206	0.216	0.188
Femur	0.231	0.205	0.270	0.197	0.297	0.164
Knee	0.389	0.321	0.404	0.274	0.370	0.290
Bone marrow	0.683	0.757	0.739	0.628	0.770	0.638
Muscle	0.082	0.067	0.083	0.071	0.068	0.081
Brain	0.019	0.018	0.017	0.014	0.014	0.014

Table S9. Biodistribution of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-18 by gamma counting after intravenous administration for selected tissues at 24 h

Animal #	% ID / g					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Blood	0.423	0.465	0.384	0.407	0.376	0.375
Heart	0.347	0.330	0.327	0.321	0.298	0.313
Lung	0.606	0.606	0.579	0.529	0.658	0.576
Spleen	1.103	1.157	1.108	1.207	0.992	1.529
Liver	3.668	3.103	3.604	3.274	3.510	3.827
Pancreas	0.350	0.387	0.433	0.346	0.331	0.350
Kidney	16.859	15.661	17.091	14.830	16.925	16.514
Stomach	0.227	0.226	0.232	0.199	0.179	0.246
Stomach-duodenum	0.595	0.456	0.541	0.515	0.362	0.351
Duodenum	0.411	0.382	0.385	0.369	0.283	0.332
Intestine	0.412	0.306	0.384	0.436	0.302	0.374
Colon	0.452	0.389	0.449	0.360	0.317	0.381
Femur	0.352	0.361	0.345	0.345	0.473	0.383
Knee	0.465	0.477	0.538	0.439	0.565	0.567
Bone marrow	1.767	2.761	1.911	2.034	2.517	2.058
Muscle	0.114	0.122	0.107	0.103	0.119	0.124
Brain	0.023	0.028	0.022	0.027	0.019	0.022

Table S10. Biodistribution of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-19 by gamma counting after intravenous administration for selected tissues at 24 and 72h

Time point:	% ID / g					
	24 h			72 h		
Animal #:	1	2	3	1	2	3
Blood	0.194	0.177	0.203	0.023	0.025	0.038
Muscle	0.068	0.066	0.081	0.046	0.049	0.043
Heart	0.136	0.134	0.127	0.080	0.078	0.075
Lung	0.884	0.774	0.973	0.719	0.708	0.884
Spleen	0.339	0.339	0.311	0.269	0.272	0.287
Liver	2.136	2.191	2.015	1.140	1.493	1.311
Pancreas	0.171	0.160	0.153	0.115	0.133	0.109
Kidney	4.916	4.699	4.771	4.031	4.748	4.642
Stomach	0.155	0.150	0.164	0.088	0.139	0.101
Stomach-duodenum	0.215	0.247	0.304	0.167	0.238	0.178
Duodenum	0.140	0.152	0.156	0.088	0.105	0.079
Intestine	0.105	0.115	0.145	0.062	0.082	0.068
Colon	0.155	0.147	0.164	0.087	0.093	0.099
Femur	0.176	0.140	0.185	0.293	0.200	0.174
Knee	0.273	0.230	0.254	0.201	0.310	0.222
Bone marrow	0.860	0.545	0.528	0.347	0.536	0.283
Brain	0.009	0.009	0.009	0.004	0.004	0.003

Table S11. Average values, standard deviation and t-test p values for biodistributions of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-2 and [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-19 by gamma counting after intravenous administration for selected tissues at 24 and 72h

Time	Peptide	% ID / g								
		Blood	Muscle	Lung	Spleen	Liver	Bone marrow	Kidney	Brain	Pancreas
24 h	[Zr ⁸⁹]Zr-2	0.23 ± 0.04	0.07 ± 0.02	1.49 ± 0.13	0.49 ± 0.06	1.1 ± 0.19	0.99 ± 0.16	8.3 ± 0.6	0.018 ± 0.004	0.203 ± 0.03
	[Zr ⁸⁹]Zr-19	0.191 ± 0.013	0.072 ± 0.008	0.88 ± 0.1	0.33 ± 0.016	2.11 ± 0.09	0.64 ± 0.19	4.795 ± 0.11	0.009 ± 0	0.161 ± 0.009
	P-value:	0.14	0.66	0.0005	0.004	0.0001	0.04	0.00006	0.007	0.050
72 h	[Zr ⁸⁹]Zr-2	0.037 ± 0.012	0.045 ± 0.008	1.1 ± 0.2	0.46 ± 0.08	0.91 ± 0.15	0.49 ± 0.13	8.6 ± 1.2	0.011 ± 0.005	0.32 ± 0.16
	[Zr ⁸⁹]Zr-19	0.029 ± 0.008	0.046 ± 0.003	0.77 ± 0.099	0.276 ± 0.0096	1.31 ± 0.18	0.39 ± 0.13	4.5 ± 0.4	0.0037 ± 0.0006	0.119 ± 0.012
	P-value:	0.33	0.85	0.08	0.010	0.012	0.35	0.0013	0.04	0.07

Figure S1. in vivo positron emission tomography (PET) images showing the bio-distribution of $[^{89}\text{Zr}]\text{Zr}$ labelled peptide **13** at 4 and 24 hours after intravenous injection: Dorsal (left), and sagittal (middle) view of upper body and dorsal view of lower body (right) Rats were injected with 16-24 MBq (4 nmol) / kg of $[^{89}\text{Zr}]\text{Zr}$ -labelled peptides. Data is expressed as the percentage of the injected dose per gram (%ID/g).

Figure S2. in vivo positron emission tomography (PET) images showing the bio-distribution of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr labelled peptide **18** at 4 and 24 hours after intravenous injection: Dorsal (left), and sagittal (middle) view of upper body and dorsal view of lower body (right) Rats were injected with 16-24 MBq (4 nmol) / kg of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-labelled peptides. Data is expressed as the percentage of the injected dose per gram (%ID/g).

Figure S3. in vivo positron emission tomography (PET) images showing the bio-distribution of $[^{89}\text{Zr}]\text{Zr}$ labelled peptides **19** and **2** at 4, 8, 24 and 72 hours after intravenous injection: Each image represent one animal. Rats were injected with 20 MBq (4 nmol) / kg of $[^{89}\text{Zr}]\text{Zr}$ -labelled peptides. Data is expressed as the percentage of the injected dose per gram (%ID/g). Images for peptide **2** were generated based on in vivo experiments from¹

Supplementary Materials and Methods

Chemicals and reagents

Standard Fmoc-protected amino acids for solid-phase peptide synthesis and OxymaPure were purchased from Gyros Protein Technologies. Boc-Lys(Boc)-OH DCHA and Fmoc-Lys(Fmoc)-OH were from Novabiochem. Alloc-Lys(Fmoc)-OH was purchased from Iris Biotech. Wang-resins were obtained from Novabiochem. N,N'-diisopropylcarbodiimide (DIC), piperidine, N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF), trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) and hexafluoroisopropanol (HFIP) were obtained from Biosolve Chemie SARL. Triisopropylsilane (TIPS), dichloromethane (DCM), N,N-Diisopropylethylamine (DIPEA), diethyl ether, 3,4-diethoxy-3-cyclobutene-1,2-dione, deferoxamine mesylate salt, Zirconium(IV) chloride, Tetrakis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(0) (Pd(PPh₃)₄), Borane dimethylamine complex (BH₃NH(CH₃)₂), and 4-(Dimethylamino)pyridine (DMAP) were purchased from Merck.

UPLC and LCMS characterization of peptides

Purified peptides were analysed by mass spectrometry on a RP-UPLC-MS system in positive ion mode using electrospray ionisation (Waters Acquity UPLC H Class with Waters Acquity BEH C-18 column, 1.7µm, 2.1 x 50 mm with either Waters Xevo G2-XS QToF detector, for high resolution, or Waters QDa detector). MassLynx V4.2 software (for QToF) or empower (For QDa) was used for analysing the mass spectra. For zirconium containing peptides, a net charge of +1 of the zirconium-DFO complex was used in the calculations.

The purity of the peptides was determined by analytical RP-UPLC (Waters Acquity UPLC H Class) using different methods as indicated below. Solvent B (MeCN, 0.05% [v/v] TFA) was run at a gradient in solvent A (H₂O, 0.05% [v/v] TFA). The column temperature was 40°C and absorbance was detected at 214 nm (Waters Acquity PDA Detector) for all methods.

Table S12. UPLC methods used for characterization

Method	Gradient (% B)	Gradient time (min)	Total time (min)	column	Flow (ml/min)
A	25-75	4	7	Acquity UPLC BEH300 C18 1.7µm, 2.1 x 50mm	0.4
B	5-95	3.5	6	Acquity UPLC BEH300 C18 1.7µm, 2.1 x 50mm	0.45
C	5-60	3.5	6	Acquity UPLC BEH300 C18 1.7µm, 2.1 x 50mm	0.45
D	25-75	10	13	Acquity UPLC BEH300 C18 1.7µm, 2.1 x 150mm	0.4
E	5-95	16	20	Acquity UPLC BEH300 C18 1.7µm, 2.1 x 150mm	0.4

Concentration determination of peptides

Peptides were quantified by Charged Aerosol Detection (CAD) on a LC-CAD system (Thermo-Fisher Vanquish) using an analytical C18 column (Waters CSH C-18, 130Å, 1.7 µm, 2.1 x 50 mm) and a linear gradient of 0–80% solvent B (MeCN, 0.1% [v/v] TFA) in solvent A (H₂O, 0.1% [v/v] TFA) over 4 minutes at a flow rate of 0.3 ml min⁻¹. Quantification was performed using the signal from a CAD detector (Thermo-Fisher Vanquish Charged Aerosol Detector H) and Insulin Aspart was used as external standard.

Molecular modelling of peptide **18**

Peptide **18** was modelled taking the coordinates of semaglutide bound to a GLP-1R-Gs complex as starting point (PDB ID 7K10). Addition of explicit hydrogens and estimation of most probable side chain protonation states was performed with Schrödinger's Protein Preparation Wizard² and structural modifications were done interactively in Maestro³. The latter included the deamination of the N-terminal histidine, side chain mutations along semaglutide's alpha helix, and extension of an alpha helical structure for the seven C-terminal residues of **18** that lacked template residues from semaglutide coordinates. Finally, lysine conjugations were built by manual selection of dihedral angles, the use of partial molecular mechanics energy minimizations, and taking the environment provided by the peptide binding site of GLP-1R into account.

Zirconium-89 radiolabelling and radio-stability assay

DFO modified peptides were radiolabelled with [⁸⁹Zr][Zr(C₂O₄)₄]⁴⁻ (zirconium-oxalate) using the following procedure. The pH of the [⁸⁹Zr][Zr(C₂O₄)₄]⁴⁻ in solution was adjusted to pH 7.4 using 2 M Na₂CO₃ before adding 0.5M HEPES (pH 7.4). Subsequently peptides in vehicle (50 mM phosphate buffer, 70 mM NaCl, 70 ppm Tween20, pH 7.4) were added to the [⁸⁹Zr][Zr(C₂O₄)₄]⁴⁻ and incubated at 37°C at 300 rpm for 1 h. The radiolabeling efficiency was determined using iTLC with NH₄-EDTA mobile phase. Unbound [⁸⁹Zr][Zr(C₂O₄)₄]⁴⁻ was removed using 7 kDa ZEBRA spin columns according to the manufactures instructions. After purification, the bound and unbound [⁸⁹Zr][Zr(C₂O₄)₄]⁴⁻ was determined again using iTLC.

The radio-stability of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr labelled peptides was measured after incubation in PBS (pH 7.4), fetal calf serum or EDTA/PBS (1000 equiv EDTA) at 37°C for 1h, 2h, 4h, 24h and 168h at 300 rpm by determining the bound and released [⁸⁹Zr]Zr using iTLC.

Statistical analysis

A two-tailed student's t-test was applied to determine the significance of the difference in tissue uptake of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**2** and [⁸⁹Zr]Zr-**19**. Analysis was performed in Microsoft Excel.

	Retention Time	% Area
1	9.135	100.00

UPLC method: E

Figure S4. UPLC analysis of 1

	Retention Time	% Area
1	8.522	90.9
	8.682	9.1

UPLC method: E

Figure S5. UPLC analysis of 2

	Retention Time	% Area
1	3.128	4.75
2	3.165	90.28
3	3.215	4.96

UPLC method: B

Figure S6. UPLC analysis of 3

	Retention Time	% Area
1	6.228	3.88
2	6.426	81.75
3	6.554	12.38
4	6.634	1.98

UPLC method: D

Figure S7. UPLC analysis of 4

	Retention Time	% Area
1	6.561	2.84
2	6.824	92.08
3	7.090	5.08

UPLC method: D

Figure S8. UPLC analysis of 5

	Retention Time	% Area
1	6.524	2.32
2	6.785	92.65
3	7.081	3.72
4	7.160	1.31

UPLC method: D

Figure S9. UPLC analysis of 6

	Retention Time	% Area
1	6.491	2.11
2	6.610	1.64
3	6.747	96.25

UPLC method: D

Figure S10. UPLC analysis of **7**

	Retention Time	% Area
1	3.181	91.31
2	3.236	8.69

UPLC method: B

Figure S11. UPLC analysis of **8**

	Retention Time	% Area
1	3.228	95.12
2	3.290	4.88

UPLC method: B

Figure S12. UPLC analysis of 9

	Retention Time	% Area
1	8.122	2.48
2	8.309	90.16
3	8.454	7.35

UPLC method: E

Figure S13. UPLC analysis of 10

	Retention Time	% Area
1	8.854	94.40
2	8.994	5.60

UPLC method: E

Figure S14. UPLC analysis of 11

	Retention Time	% Area
1	8.361	91.76
2	8.476	8.24

UPLC method: E

Figure S15. UPLC analysis of 12

	Retention Time	% Area
1	8.658	6.70
2	8.818	93.30

UPLC method: E

Figure S16. UPLC analysis of **13**

	Retention Time	% Area
1	8.166	8.81
2	8.296	91.19

UPLC method: E

Figure S17. UPLC analysis of **14**

	Retention Time	% Area
1	8.144	9.98
2	8.237	90.02

UPLC method: E

Figure S18. UPLC analysis of 15

	Retention Time	% Area
1	8.404	8.93
2	8.554	91.07

UPLC method: E

Figure S19. UPLC analysis of 16

	Retention Time	% Area
1	8.416	100.00

UPLC method: E

Figure S20. UPLC analysis of 17

	Retention Time	% Area
1	8.377	100.00

UPLC method: E

Figure S21. UPLC analysis of 18

	Retention Time	% Area
1	8.187	100.00

UPLC method: E

Figure S22. UPLC analysis of 19

	Retention Time	% Area
1	2.331	100.00

UPLC method: A

Figure S23. UPLC analysis of Zr-3

	Retention Time	% Area
1	3.089	100.00

UPLC method: B

Figure S24. UPLC analysis of Zr-4

	Retention Time	% Area
1	3.108	3.49
2	3.159	96.51

UPLC method: B

Figure S25. UPLC analysis of Zr-5

	Retention Time	% Area
1	3.041	2.97
2	3.094	4.02
3	3.137	93.02

UPLC method: B

Figure S26. UPLC analysis of Zr-6

SampleName: JT5-DFO-Zr_F32 Instrument Method Name: TFA_C18_short_25_75_7min

	Retention Time	% Area
1	2.327	2.85
2	2.394	97.15

UPLC method: A

Figure S27. UPLC analysis of Zr-7

	Retention Time	% Area
1	4.024	100.00

UPLC method: C

Figure S28. UPLC analysis of Zr-8

	Retention Time	% Area
1	4.034	3.29
2	4.110	96.71

UPLC method: C

Figure S29. UPLC analysis of Zr-9

	Retention Time	% Area
1	7.968	90.31
2	8.148	5.40
3	8.295	4.30

UPLC method: E

Figure S30. UPLC analysis of Zr-10

	Retention Time	% Area
1	7.962	2.98
2	8.477	4.91
3	8.525	92.11

UPLC method: E

Figure S31. UPLC analysis of Zr-11

	Retention Time	% Area
1	8.143	100.00

UPLC method: E

Figure S32. UPLC analysis of Zr-12

	Retention Time	% Area
1	8.186	100.00

UPLC method: E

Figure S33. UPLC analysis of Zr-13

	Retention Time	% Area
1	7.928	89.51
2	8.106	10.49

UPLC method: E

Figure S34. UPLC analysis of Zr-14

	Retention Time	% Area
1	7.806	100.00

UPLC method: E

Figure S35. UPLC analysis of Zr-15

	Retention Time	% Area
1	8.120	96.18
2	8.541	3.82

UPLC method: E

Figure S36. UPLC analysis of Zr-16

	Retention Time	% Area
1	7.917	91.16
2	8.117	8.84

UPLC method: E

Figure S37. UPLC analysis of Zr-17

	Retention Time	% Area
1	8.531	100.00

UPLC method: E

Figure S38. UPLC analysis of Zr-18

	Retention Time	% Area
1	8.384	11.46
2	8.460	88.54

UPLC method: E

Figure S39. UPLC analysis of Zr-19

Average, calculated						
MW (Da)	[M+3H] ³⁺	[M+4H] ⁴⁺	[M+5H] ⁵⁺	[M+6H] ⁶⁺	[M+7H] ⁷⁺	[M+8H] ⁸⁺
4255.733	1419.7	1065.0	852.2	710.4	609.0	533.0

Analysed using QDa detector

Figure S40. Mass spectrometry analysis of **1**

Average, calculated						
MW (Da)	[M+3H] ³⁺	[M+4H] ⁴⁺	[M+5H] ⁵⁺	[M+6H] ⁶⁺	[M+7H] ⁷⁺	[M+8H] ⁸⁺
5223.7953	1742.3	1307.0	1045.8	871.7	747.3	654.0

Analysed using QDa detector

Figure S41. Mass spectrometry analysis of **2**

Average, calculated						
MW (Da)	$[M+3H]^{3+}$	$[M+4H]^{4+}$	$[M+5H]^{5+}$	$[M+6H]^{6+}$	$[M+7H]^{7+}$	$[M+8H]^{8+}$
5990.6773	1998.0	1498.7	1199.2	999.5	856.9	749.9

Figure S42. Mass spectrometry analysis of 3

Average, calculated						
MW (Da)	$[M+3H]^{3+}$	$[M+4H]^{4+}$	$[M+5H]^{5+}$	$[M+6H]^{6+}$	$[M+7H]^{7+}$	$[M+8H]^{8+}$
5834.4916	1945.9	1459.7	1168.0	973.5	834.6	730.4

Figure S43. Mass spectrometry analysis of 6

Average, calculated						
MW (Da)	[M+3H] ³⁺	[M+4H] ⁴⁺	[M+5H] ⁵⁺	[M+6H] ⁶⁺	[M+7H] ⁷⁺	[M+8H] ⁸⁺
5834.4916	1945.9	1459.7	1168.0	973.5	834.6	730.4

Figure S44. Mass spectrometry analysis of 7

Average, calculated						
MW (Da)	[M+3H] ³⁺	[M+4H] ⁴⁺	[M+5H] ⁵⁺	[M+6H] ⁶⁺	[M+7H] ⁷⁺	[M+8H] ⁸⁺
5561.252	1854.8	1391.4	1113.3	927.9	795.5	696.2

Analysed using QDa detector

Figure S45. Mass spectrometry analysis of 8

Average, calculated						
MW (Da)	[M+3H] ³⁺	[M+4H] ⁴⁺	[M+5H] ⁵⁺	[M+6H] ⁶⁺	[M+7H] ⁷⁺	[M+8H] ⁸⁺
5534.181	1845.8	1384.6	1107.9	923.4	791.7	692.8

Analysed using QDa detector

Figure S46. Mass spectrometry analysis of 9

jwlb

JWLB_11Mar2020_JT8-DFO_pruif-F12-14 171 (2.941) Cm (171)

1: TOF MS ES+
2.11e6

Average, calculated						
MW (Da)	[M+3H] ³⁺	[M+4H] ⁴⁺	[M+5H] ⁵⁺	[M+6H] ⁶⁺	[M+7H] ⁷⁺	[M+8H] ⁸⁺
5891.5463	1964.9	1474.0	1179.4	983.0	842.7	737.5

Figure S47. Mass spectrometry analysis of 10

jwlb

JWLB_11Mar2020_JT9-DFO_pruif-F12-14 180 (3.095) Cm (180)

1: TOF MS ES+
2.44e6

Average, calculated						
MW (Da)	[M+3H] ³⁺	[M+4H] ⁴⁺	[M+5H] ⁵⁺	[M+6H] ⁶⁺	[M+7H] ⁷⁺	[M+8H] ⁸⁺
5504.1977	1835.8	1377.1	1101.9	918.4	787.4	689.1

Figure S48. Mass spectrometry analysis of 11

jwlb

JWLB_28Apr_JT10-DFO_pool 173 (2.975) Cm (172:174)

1: TOF MS ES+
6.78e6

Average, calculated						
MW (Da)	[M+3H] ³⁺	[M+4H] ⁴⁺	[M+5H] ⁵⁺	[M+6H] ⁶⁺	[M+7H] ⁷⁺	[M+8H] ⁸⁺
5861.5633	1954.9	1466.5	1173.4	978.0	838.4	733.8

Figure S49. Mass spectrometry analysis of 12

jwlb

JWLB_19May_JT12-DFO_F14 171 (2.941) Cm (171:172)

1: TOF MS ES+
7.51e5

Average, calculated						
MW (Da)	[M+3H] ³⁺	[M+4H] ⁴⁺	[M+5H] ⁵⁺	[M+6H] ⁶⁺	[M+7H] ⁷⁺	[M+8H] ⁸⁺
7159.9192	2387.7	1791.1	1433.1	1194.4	1023.9	896.1

Figure S50. Mass spectrometry analysis of 14

jwlb

JWLB_19May_JT13-DFO_F14 171 (2.941) Cm (170:173)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.59e6

Average, calculated						
MW (Da)	[M+3H] ³⁺	[M+4H] ⁴⁺	[M+5H] ⁵⁺	[M+6H] ⁶⁺	[M+7H] ⁷⁺	[M+8H] ⁸⁺
8127.9812	2710.4	2033.1	1626.7	1355.7	1162.2	1017.1

Figure S51. Mass spectrometry analysis of 15

High Resolution Mass Spectrometry

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of Zr-3

Molecular structure

Icms34

JWLB_19Nov2019_JT1-DFO-Zr 224 (3.954) Cm (224:225)

1: TOF MS ES+
4.53e6

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

Icms34

JWL B_19Nov2019_JT1-DFO-Zr 224 (3.954) Cm (224:225)

1: TOF MS ES+
7.47e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+2H]^{4+}$

Icms34

JWL B_19Nov2019_JT1-DFO-Zr 224 (3.954) Cm (224:225)

1: TOF MS ES+
4.53e6

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+3H]^{5+}$

Icms34

JWLB_19Nov2019_JT1-DFO-Zr 224 (3.954) Cm (224:225)

1: TOF MS ES+
2.15e6

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+4H]^{6+}$

	MW	$[M+H]^{3+}$	$[M+2H]^{4+}$	$[M+3H]^{5+}$	$[M+4H]^{6+}$
Calculated (Da)	6160.872	2053.960	1540.722	1232.779	1027.484
Observed (Da)	6160.853		1540.719	1232.768	1027.485
Error (ppm)		-3			

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of Zr-4

Molecular structure

lcms34

JWL B_30Oct2019_JT2DFOZr_RM_5min 217 (3.836) Cm (214:219)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.07e5

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

lcms34

JWLB_30Oct2019_JT2DFOZr_RM_5min 217 (3.836) Cm (214:219)

1: TOF MS ES+
2.49e4

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+2H]^{4+}$

lcms34

JWLB_30Oct2019_JT2DFOZr_RM_5min 217 (3.836) Cm (214:219)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.07e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+3H]^{5+}$

lcms34

JWL B_30Oct2019_JT2DFOZr_RM_5min 217 (3.836) Cm (214:219)

1: TOF MS ES+
4.56e4

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+4H]^{6+}$

	MW	$[M+H]^{3+}$	$[M+2H]^{4+}$	$[M+3H]^{5+}$	$[M+4H]^{6+}$
Calculated (Da)	6361.947	2120.985	1590.990	1272.994	1060.996
Observed (Da)	6361.83		1590.953	1272.967	1060.985
Error (ppm)		-18			

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of Zr-5

Exact Mass : 6004.770916(5)
Formula : C₂₆₄H₄₁₀N₆₂O₉₆Zr₂

Molecular structure

Icms34

JWLB_30Oct2019_JT3DFOZr_RM_5min 221 (3.904) Cm (218:224)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.02e5

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

Icms34

JWLB_30Oct2019_JT3DFOZr_RM_5min 221 (3.904) Cm (218:224)

1: TOF MS ES+
4.03e4

Icms34

JWLB_30Oct2019_JT3DFOZr_RM_5min 221 (3.904) Cm (218:224)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.02e5

Icms34

JWLb_30Oct2019_JT3DFOZr_RM_5min 221 (3.904) Cm (218:224)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.23e4

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+4H]^{6+}$

	MW	$[M+H]^{3+}$	$[M+2H]^{4+}$	$[M+3H]^{5+}$	$[M+4H]^{6+}$
Calculated (Da)	6004.771	2001.926	1501.696	1201.559	1001.467
Observed (Da)	6004.696		1501.673	1201.538	1001.462
Error (ppm)	-12				

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of Zr-6

Molecular structure

Icms34

JWLB_30Oct2019_JT4DFOZr_RM_5min 224 (3.954) Cm (223:225)

1: TOF MS ES+
4.14e5

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

Icms34

JWLB_30Oct2019_JT4DFOZr_RM_5min 224 (3.954) Cm (223:225)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.50e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+2H]^{4+}$

Icms34

JWLB_30Oct2019_JT4DFOZr_RM_5min 224 (3.954) Cm (223:225)

1: TOF MS ES+
4.14e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+3H]^{5+}$

Icms34

JWL B_30Oct2019_JT4DFOZr_RM_5min 224 (3.954) Cm (223:225)

1: TOF MS ES+
5.04e4

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+4H]^{6+}$

	MW	$[M+H]^{3+}$	$[M+2H]^{4+}$	$[M+3H]^{5+}$	$[M+4H]^{6+}$
Calculated (Da)	6004.771	2001.926	1501.696	1201.559	1001.467
Observed (Da)	6004.696		1501.673	1201.538	1001.462
Error (ppm)	-12				

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of Zr-7

Molecular structure

Icms34

JWL B_30Oct2019_JT5DFOZr_RM_5min 225 (3.971) Cm (225:226)

1: TOF MS ES+
2.99e5

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

Icms34

JWLb_30Oct2019_JT5DFOZr_RM_5min 225 (3.971) Cm (225:226)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.10e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+2H]^{4+}$

Icms34

JWLb_30Oct2019_JT5DFOZr_RM_5min 225 (3.971) Cm (225:226)

1: TOF MS ES+
2.99e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+3H]^{5+}$

Icms34

JWL B_30Oct2019_JT5DFOZr_RM_5min 225 (3.971) Cm (225:226)

1: TOF MS ES+
3.98e4

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+4H]^{6+}$

	MW	$[M+H]^{3+}$	$[M+2H]^{4+}$	$[M+3H]^{5+}$	$[M+4H]^{6+}$
Calculated (Da)	6004.771	2001.926	1501.696	1201.559	1001.467
Observed (Da)	6004.67		1501.673	1201.538	1001.449
Error (ppm)	-17				

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of Zr-8

Molecular structure

Icms34

JWLB_19Nov2019_JT6-DFO-Zr 224 (3.954) Cm (223:225)

1: TOF MS ES+
9.58e6

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

Icms34

JWLB_19Nov2019_JT6-DFO-Zr 224 (3.954) Cm (223:225)

1: TOF MS ES+
5.20e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+H]^{3+}$

Icms34

JWLB_19Nov2019_JT6-DFO-Zr 224 (3.954) Cm (223:225)

1: TOF MS ES+
2.67e6

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+2H]^{4+}$

Icms34

JWLB_19Nov2019_JT6-DFO-Zr 224 (3.954) Cm (223:225)

1: TOF MS ES+
9.58e6

Mass spectrum zoom of [M+3H]⁵⁺

Icms34

JWLB_19Nov2019_JT6-DFO-Zr 224 (3.954) Cm (223:225)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.80e6

Mass spectrum zoom of [M+4H]⁶⁺

	Monoisotopic				
	MW	[M+H] ³⁺	[M+2H] ⁴⁺	[M+3H] ⁵⁺	[M+4H] ⁶⁺
Calculated (Da)	5731.686	1910.898	1433.425	1146.942	955.953
Observed (Da)	5731.667	1910.892	1433.421	1146.935	955.951
Error (ppm)		-3			

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of Zr-9

Exact Mass : 5704.627547(5)
 Formula : C₂₅₂H₃₉₀N₅₈O₈₁Zr₂

Molecular structure

lcms34

JWLB_19Nov2019_JT7-DFO-Zr 227 (4.005) Cm (227:228)

1: TOF MS ES+
5.77e6

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

Icms34

JWLB_19Nov2019_JT7-DFO-Zr 227 (4.005) Cm (227:228)

1: TOF MS ES+
3.36e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+H]^{3+}$

Icms34

JWLB_19Nov2019_JT7-DFO-Zr 227 (4.005) Cm (227:228)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.98e6

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+2H]^{4+}$

Icms34

JWL B_19Nov2019_JT7-DFO-Zr 227 (4.005) Cm (227:228)

1: TOF MS ES+
5.77e6Mass spectrum zoom of [M+3H]⁵⁺**Icms34**

JWL B_19Nov2019_JT7-DFO-Zr 227 (4.005) Cm (227:228)

1: TOF MS ES+
3.54e5Mass spectrum zoom of [M+4H]⁶⁺

	MW	[M+H] ³⁺	[M+2H] ⁴⁺	[M+3H] ⁵⁺	[M+4H] ⁶⁺
Calculated (Da)	5704.627	1901.878	1426.660	1141.530	951.443
Observed (Da)	5704.609	1901.87	1426.66	1141.524	951.44
Error (ppm)		-3			

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of Zr-10

Exact Mass : 6061.803613(5)
 Formula : C₂₆₅H₄₁₃N₆₅O₈₆Zr₂

Molecular structure

jwlb

JWLB_11May_JT8-DFO-Zr_pool 167 (2.872) Cm (166:167)

1: TOF MS ES+
6.41e6

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

jwlb

JWLB_11May_JT8-DFO-Zr_pool 167 (2.872) Cm (166:167)

1: TOF MS ES+
6.46e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+H]^{3+}$

jwlb

JWLB_11May_JT8-DFO-Zr_pool 167 (2.872) Cm (166:167)

1: TOF MS ES+
3.00e6

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+2H]^{4+}$

jwlb

JWLB_11May_JT8-DFO-Zr_pool 167 (2.872) Cm (166:167)

1: TOF MS ES+
6.41e6

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+3H]^{5+}$

jwlb

JWLB_11May_JT8-DFO-Zr_pool 167 (2.872) Cm (166:167)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.84e6

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+4H]^{6+}$

	MW	$[M+H]^{3+}$	$[M+2H]^{4+}$	$[M+3H]^{5+}$	$[M+4H]^{6+}$
Calculated (Da)	6061.804	2020.937	1515.955	1212.965	1010.972
Observed (Da)	6061.452	2020.818	1515.868	1212.899	1010.91
Error (ppm)		-58			

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of Zr-11

Molecular structure

Icms34

JWLB_4May2020_JT9-DFO_aftZr 177 (3.044) Cm (176:178)

1: TOF MS ES+
4.74e4

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

Icms34

JWL B_4May2020_JT9-DFO_ aftZr 177 (3.044) Cm (176:178)

1: TOF MS ES+
4.21e4

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+2H]^{4+}$

Icms34

JWL B_4May2020_JT9-DFO_ aftZr 177 (3.044) Cm (176:178)

1: TOF MS ES+
4.74e4

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+3H]^{5+}$

Icms34

JWL B_4May2020_JT9-DFO_aptZr 177 (3.044) Cm (176:178)

1: TOF MS ES+
3.49e3

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+4H]^{6+}$

	MW	$[M+H]^{3+}$	$[M+2H]^{4+}$	$[M+3H]^{5+}$	$[M+4H]^{6+}$
Calculated (Da)	5674.653	1891.887	1419.167	1135.535	946.447
Observed (Da)	5674.317		1419.084	1135.454	946.402
Error (ppm)	-59				

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of Zr-12

Exact Mass : 6031.829434(5)
Formula : C₂₆₅H₄₁₅N₆₅O₆₄Zr₂

Molecular structure

Icms34

JWL B_4May2020_JT10-DFO_aptZr 170 (2.924) Cm (169:170)

1: TOF MS ES+
2.05e5

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

Icms34

JWLB_4May2020_JT10-DFO_aptZr 170 (2.924) Cm (169:170)

1: TOF MS ES+
8.75e4

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+2H]^{4+}$

Icms34

JWLB_4May2020_JT10-DFO_aptZr 170 (2.924) Cm (169:170)

1: TOF MS ES+
2.05e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+3H]^{5+}$

Icms34

JWL B_4May2020_JT10-DFO_ aftZr 170 (2.924) Cm (169:170)

1: TOF MS ES+
3.61e4

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+4H]^{6+}$

	MW	$[M+H]^{3+}$	$[M+2H]^{4+}$	$[M+3H]^{5+}$	$[M+4H]^{6+}$
Calculated (Da)	6031.829	2010.945	1508.461	1206.970	1005.976
Observed (Da)	6031.395		1508.356	1206.877	1005.907
Error (ppm)	-72				

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of Zr-13

Molecular structure

jwlb

JWLB_6May_JT11-Zr_F1-7 169 (2.907) Cm (169)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.38e6

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

jwlb

JWLB_6May_JT11-Zr_F1-7 169 (2.907) Cm (169)

1: TOF MS ES+
9.42e4

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+H]^{3+}$

jwlb

JWLB_6May_JT11-Zr_F1-7 169 (2.907) Cm (169)

1: TOF MS ES+
5.68e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+2H]^{4+}$

jwlb

JWLB_6May_JT11-Zr_F1-7 169 (2.907) Cm (169)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.38e6

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+3H]^{5+}$

jwlb

JWLB_6May_JT11-Zr_F1-7 169 (2.907) Cm (169)

1: TOF MS ES+
4.27e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+4H]^{6+}$

Monoisotopic

	MW	$[M+H]^{3+}$	$[M+2H]^{4+}$	$[M+3H]^{5+}$	$[M+4H]^{6+}$
Calculated (Da)	6160.872	2053.960	1540.722	1232.779	1027.484
Observed (Da)	6160.493	2053.83	1540.619	1232.706	1027.425
Error (ppm)		-61			

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of Zr-14

Molecular structure

jwlb

JWLB_28May_JT12-DFO-Zr_F55-56 166 (2.855) Cm (165:168)

1: TOF MS ES+
4.50e5

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

jwlb

JWLB_28May_JT12-DFO-Zr_F55-56 166 (2.855) Cm (165:168)

1: TOF MS ES+
7.92e4

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+H]^{4+}$

jwlb

JWLB_28May_JT12-DFO-Zr_F55-56 166 (2.855) Cm (165:168)

1: TOF MS ES+
4.50e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+2H]^{5+}$

jwlb

JWLB_28May_JT12-DFO-Zr_F55-56 166 (2.855) Cm (165:168)

1: TOF MS ES+
2.98e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+3H]^{6+}$

jwlb

JWLB_28May_JT12-DFO-Zr_F55-56 166 (2.855) Cm (165:168)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.34e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+4H]^{7+}$

Monoisotopic

	MW	$[M]^{3+}$	$[M+H]^{4+}$	$[M+2H]^{5+}$	$[M+3H]^{6+}$	$[M+4H]^{7+}$
Calculated (Da)	7416.326	2472.109	1854.333	1483.668	1236.558	1060.051
Observed (Da)	7417.034		1854.5	1483.819	1236.675	1060.15
Error (ppm)	95					

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of Zr-15

Molecular structure

lcms34

JWL B_30Jun_JT13-DFO-Zr_F5-9 164 (2.821) Cm (164:165)

1: TOF MS ES+
4.03e5

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

Icms34

JWL B_30Jun_JT13-DFO-Zr_F5-9 164 (2.821) Cm (164:165)

1: TOF MS ES+
2.36e4

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M]^{4+}$

Icms34

JWL B_30Jun_JT13-DFO-Zr_F5-9 164 (2.821) Cm (164:165)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.61e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+H]^{5+}$

Icms34

JWLB_30Jun_JT13-DFO-Zr_F5-9 164 (2.821) Cm (164:165)

1: TOF MS ES+
4.03e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+2H]^{6+}$

Icms34

JWLB_30Jun_JT13-DFO-Zr_F5-9 164 (2.821) Cm (164:165)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.22e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+3H]^{7+}$

Icms34

JWL B_30Jun_JT13-DFO-Zr_F5-9 164 (2.821) Cm (164:165)

1: TOF MS ES+
8.56e4

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+4H]^{8+}$

	Monoisotopic					
	MW	$[M]^{4+}$	$[M+H]^{5+}$	$[M+2H]^{6+}$	$[M+3H]^{7+}$	$[M+4H]^{8+}$
Calculated (Da)	8470.704	2117.676	1694.342	1412.120	1210.532	1059.342
Observed (Da)	8472.309	2117.923	1694.716	1412.446	1210.662	1059.457
Error (ppm)	189					

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of Zr-16

Molecular structure

jwlb

JWLB_28May_JT14-DFO-Zr_F48-49 170 (2.924) Cm (170:171)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.85e6

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

juwb

JWLB_28May_JT14-DFO-Zr_F48-49 170 (2.924) Cm (170:171)

1: TOF MS ES+
6.81e4

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M]^{3+}$

juwb

JWLB_28May_JT14-DFO-Zr_F48-49 170 (2.924) Cm (170:171)

1: TOF MS ES+
3.60e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+H]^{4+}$

jwlb

JWLB_28May_JT14-DFO-Zr_F48-49 170 (2.924) Cm (170:171)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.85e6

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+2H]^{5+}$

jwlb

JWLB_28May_JT14-DFO-Zr_F48-49 170 (2.924) Cm (170:171)

1: TOF MS ES+
8.12e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+3H]^{6+}$

Monoisotopic

	MW	$[M]^{3+}$	$[M+H]^{4+}$	$[M+2H]^{5+}$	$[M+3H]^{6+}$
Calculated (Da)	7059.15	2353.050	1765.039	1412.233	1177.029
Observed (Da)	7059.879	2353.288	1765.221	1412.385	1177.148
Error (ppm)		103			

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of Zr-17

Molecular structure

jwlb

JWL B_28May_JT15-DFO-Zr_F45 167 (2.872) Cm (167)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.72e5

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

jwlb

JWLB_28May_JT15-DFO-Zr_F45 167 (2.872) Cm (167)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.90e4

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M]^{4+}$

jwlb

JWLB_28May_JT15-DFO-Zr_F45 167 (2.872) Cm (167)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.42e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+H]^{5+}$

juwb

JWLB_28May_JT15-DFO-Zr_F45 167 (2.872) Cm (167)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.72e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+2H]^{6+}$

juwb

JWLB_28May_JT15-DFO-Zr_F45 167 (2.872) Cm (167)

1: TOF MS ES+
6.16e4

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+3H]^{7+}$

	MW	$[M-H]^{3+}$	$[M]^{4+}$	$[M+H]^{5+}$	$[M+2H]^{6+}$	$[M+3H]^{7+}$
Calculated (Da)	8113.528	2704.174	2028.382	1622.907	1352.590	1159.507
Observed (Da)	8114.168		2028.534	1623.042	1352.689	1159.605
Error (ppm)		79				

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of Zr-18

Molecular structure

jwlb

JWLB_11Apr_280-3_Zeba_4X 154 (2.858) Cm (153:154)

1: TOF MS ES+
3.67e6

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

jwlb

JWLB_11Apr_280-3_Zeba_4X 154 (2.858) Cm (153:154)

1: TOF MS ES+
9.71e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M]^{4+}$

jwlb

JWLB_11Apr_280-3_Zeba_4X 154 (2.858) Cm (153:154)

1: TOF MS ES+
3.67e6

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+H]^{5+}$

jwlb

JWLB_11Apr_280-3_Zeba_4X 154 (2.858) Cm (153:154)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.97e6

Mass spectrum zoom of [M+2H]⁶⁺

	MW	[M-H] ³⁺	[M] ⁴⁺	[M+H] ⁵⁺	[M+2H] ⁶⁺	[M+3H] ⁷⁺
Calculated (Da)	7867.479	2622.157	1966.870	1573.697	1311.582	1124.357
Observed (Da)	7868.344		1967.094	1573.868	1311.723	
Error (ppm)	110					

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of Zr-19

Molecular structure

lcms34

JWLb_30Jun_JT16-b1B-DFO-Zr_F1-2 172 (2.958) Cm (172:173)

1: TOF MS ES+
3.02e6

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

Icms34

JWLB_30Jun_JT16-b1B-DFO-Zr_F1-2 172 (2.958) Cm (172:173)

1: TOF MS ES+
5.68e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+2H]^{3+}$

Icms34

JWLB_30Jun_JT16-b1B-DFO-Zr_F1-2 172 (2.958) Cm (172:173)

1: TOF MS ES+
2.88e6

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+3H]^{4+}$

lcms34

JWLB_30Jun_JT16-b1B-DFO-Zr_F1-2 172 (2.958) Cm (172:173)

1: TOF MS ES+
3.02e6

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+4H]^{5+}$

	MW	$[M+2H]^{3+}$	$[M+3H]^{4+}$	$[M+4H]^{5+}$	$[M+5H]^{6+}$
Calculated (Da)	5537.677	1846.564	1385.175	1108.341	923.786
Observed (Da)	5537.663	1846.56	1385.17	1108.339	
Error (ppm)		-3			

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of 4

Exact Mass : 6188.1845261(2)
 Formula : C₂₇₇H₄₃₉N₆₉O₉₁

Molecular structure

jwlb

JWLB_11May_4663_5xEDTA 161 (2.978) Cm (160:162)

1: TOF MS ES+
8.79e7

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

jwlb

JWLB_11May_4663_5xEDTA 161 (2.978) Cm (160:162)

1: TOF MS ES+
2.16e7

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+3H]^{3+}$

jwlb

JWLB_11May_4663_5xEDTA 161 (2.978) Cm (160:162)

1: TOF MS ES+
5.56e7

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+4H]^{4+}$

jwlb

JWLB_11May_4663_5xEDTA 161 (2.978) Cm (160:162)

1: TOF MS ES+
8.79e7

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+5H]^{5+}$

jwlb

JWLB_11May_4663_5xEDTA 161 (2.978) Cm (160:162)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.16e7

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+6H]^{6+}$

Monoisotopic

	MW	$[M+3H]^{3+}$	$[M+4H]^{4+}$	$[M+5H]^{5+}$	$[M+6H]^{6+}$
Calculated (Da)	6188.185	2063.735	1548.053	1238.644	1032.371
Observed (Da)	6187.28	2063.496	1547.845	1238.451	1032.188
Error (ppm)	-146				

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of 5

Molecular structure

jwlb

JWLB_11May_4664_extra_EDTA 166 (3.075) Cm (164:168)

1: TOF MS ES+
2.50e7

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

jwlb

JWLB_11May_4664_extra_EDTA 166 (3.075) Cm (164:168)

1: TOF MS ES+
6.19e6

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+3H]^{3+}$

jwlb

JWLB_11May_4664_extra_EDTA 166 (3.075) Cm (164:168)

1: TOF MS ES+
2.50e7

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+4H]^{4+}$

jwlb

JWLB_11May_4664_extra_EDTA 166 (3.075) Cm (164:168)

1: TOF MS ES+
2.44e7

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+5H]^{5+}$

	MW	$[M+3H]^{3+}$	$[M+4H]^{4+}$	$[M+5H]^{5+}$	$[M+6H]^{6+}$
Calculated (Da)	5831.008	1944.677	1458.759	1167.209	972.842
Observed (Da)	5830.235	1944.464	1458.56	1167.032	
Error (ppm)	-133				

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of **13**

Molecular structure

lcms34

JWLB_5MAr2020_JT11DFO_purif_F20+21 152 (2.691) Cm (152)

1: TOF MS ES+
5.80e5

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

Icms34

JWLB_5MAr2020_JT11DFO_purif_F20+21 152 (2.691) Cm (152)

1: TOF MS ES+
2.24e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+4H]^{4+}$

Icms34

JWLB_5MAr2020_JT11DFO_purif_F20+21 152 (2.691) Cm (152)

1: TOF MS ES+
5.80e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+5H]^{5+}$

Icms34

JWLb_5MAr2020_JT11DFO_purif_F20+21 152 (2.691) Cm (152)

1: TOF MS ES+
6.66e4

Mass spectrum zoom of [M+6H]⁶⁺

	MW	[M+3H] ³⁺	[M+4H] ⁴⁺	[M+5H] ⁵⁺	[M+6H] ⁶⁺
Calculated (Da)	5987.11	1996.711	1497.785	1198.429	998.859
Observed (Da)	5987.292		1497.843	1198.468	998.879
Error (ppm)	30				

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of **16**

Molecular structure

jwlb

JWL B_28May_JT14-DFO_F5+6 176 (3.027) Cm (176)

1: TOF MS ES+
6.38e5

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

jwlb

JWLB_28May_JT14-DFO_F5+6 176 (3.027) Cm (176)

1: TOF MS ES+
4.92e4

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+3H]^{3+}$

jwlb

JWLB_28May_JT14-DFO_F5+6 176 (3.027) Cm (176)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.42e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+4H]^{4+}$

jwlb

JWLB_28May_JT14-DFO_F5+6 176 (3.027) Cm (176)

1: TOF MS ES+
6.38e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+5H]^{5+}$

jwlb

JWLB_28May_JT14-DFO_F5+6 176 (3.027) Cm (176)

1: TOF MS ES+
2.48e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+6H]^{6+}$

Monoisotopic

	MW	$[M+3H]^{3+}$	$[M+4H]^{4+}$	$[M+5H]^{5+}$	$[M+6H]^{6+}$
Calculated (Da)	6798.506	2267.176	1700.634	1360.709	1134.092
Observed (Da)	6798.271	2267.092	1700.584	1360.664	1134.047
Error (ppm)		-35			

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of 17

Molecular structure

jwlb

JWL B_23May_4762_EDTA 162 (2.995) Cm (161:165)

1: TOF MS ES+
3.79e7

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

jwlb

JWLB_23May_4762_EDTA 162 (2.995) Cm (161:165)

1: TOF MS ES+
7.53e6

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+4H]^{4+}$

jwlb

JWLB_23May_4762_EDTA 162 (2.995) Cm (161:165)

1: TOF MS ES+
3.79e7

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+5H]^{5+}$

jwlb

JWLB_23May_4762_EDTA 162 (2.995) Cm (161:165)

1: TOF MS ES+
2.43e7

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+6H]^{6+}$

	MW	Monoisotopic			
		$[M+3H]^{3+}$	$[M+4H]^{4+}$	$[M+5H]^{5+}$	$[M+6H]^{6+}$
Calculated (Da)	7766.003	2589.675	1942.508	1554.208	1295.341
Observed (Da)	7765.787		1942.479	1554.165	1295.288
Error (ppm)		-28			

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of **18**

Molecular structure

lcms54

JWLB_24Mar_265_RM7_pur2_Fr14-16_3xFA 160 (2.961) Cm (160:162)

1: TOF MS ES+
9.02e6

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-3000

Icms54

JWLB_24Mar_265_RM7_pur2_Fr14-16_3xFA 160 (2.961) Cm (160:162)

1: TOF MS ES+
3.04e5

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+3H]^{3+}$

Icms54

JWLB_24Mar_265_RM7_pur2_Fr14-16_3xFA 160 (2.961) Cm (160:162)

1: TOF MS ES+
1.96e6

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+4H]^{4+}$

Icms54

JWLB_24Mar_265_RM7_pur2_Fr14-16_3xFA 160 (2.961) Cm (160:162)

1: TOF MS ES+
9.02e6

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+5H]^{5+}$

Icms54

JWLB_24Mar_265_RM7_pur2_Fr14-16_3xFA 160 (2.961) Cm (160:162)

1: TOF MS ES+
7.14e6

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+6H]^{6+}$

Monoisotopic

	MW	$[M+3H]^{3+}$	$[M+4H]^{4+}$	$[M+5H]^{5+}$	$[M+6H]^{6+}$
Calculated (Da)	7519.955	2507.659	1880.996	1504.998	1254.333
Observed (Da)	7519.961	2507.665	1880.997	1504.998	1254.334
Error (ppm)		1			

High resolution mass spectrometry analysis of 19

Molecular structure

jwlb

JWLB_20May_4771_EDTA 162 (2.995) Cm (162:163)

1: TOF MS ES+
7.50e7

Mass spectrum showing m/z range 500-2500

jwlb

JWLB_20May_4771_EDTA 162 (2.995) Cm (162:163)

1: TOF MS ES+
3.77e7

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+3H]^{3+}$

jwlb

JWLB_20May_4771_EDTA 162 (2.995) Cm (162:163)

1: TOF MS ES+
7.50e7

Mass spectrum zoom of $[M+4H]^{4+}$

jwlb

JWLB_20May_4771_EDTA 162 (2.995) Cm (162:163)

1: TOF MS ES+
3.56e7

Mass spectrum zoom of [M+5H]⁵⁺

	MW	[M+3H] ³⁺	[M+4H] ⁴⁺	[M+5H] ⁵⁺	[M+6H] ⁶⁺
Calculated (Da)	5450.796	1817.939	1363.706	1091.167	909.473
Observed (Da)	5449.892	1817.676	1363.479	1090.964	
Error (ppm)	-166				

Figure S52. iTLC analysis of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr labelled peptide **13**

Profiles

Profile:

Peak	Integral [QL]	Integral [%]	Bkg [QL]	Integral-Bkg [QL]	Integral-Bkg [%]	RF Value	Start Pos. [mm]	End Pos. [mm]
1	8760416.6	89.8	48913.3	8711503.3	91.0	--	6.0	20.2
2	991084.6	10.2	34450.8	856633.9	9.0	--	50.5	59.8

Figure S53. iTLC integration profile of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr labelled peptide **13**

Figure S54. iTLC analysis of $[^{89}\text{Zr}]\text{Zr}$ labelled peptide **18**

Profiles

Profile:

Peak	Integral [cnts]	Integral [%]	Bkg [cnts]	Integral-Bkg [cnts]	Integral-Bkg [%]	RF Value	Start Pos. [mm]	End Pos. [mm]
1	26555492.0	96.2	0.0	26555492.0	96.2	--	0.0	10.3
2	1061009.4	3.8	0.0	1061009.4	3.8	--	10.7	83.2

Figure S55. iTLC integration profile of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr labelled peptide **18**

Figure S56. iTLC analysis of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr labelled peptide **19**

Profiles

Profile:

Peak	Integral [QL]	Integral [%]	Bkg [QL]	Integral-Bkg [QL]	Integral-Bkg [%]	RF Value	Start Pos. [mm]	End Pos. [mm]
1	7526555.6	99.0	0.0	27526555.6	99.0	--	8.3	41.4
2	285582.3	1.0	0.0	285582.3	1.0	--	41.5	70.3

Figure S57. iTLC integration profile of [⁸⁹Zr]Zr labelled peptide 19

References

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